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NATURAL HERITAGE, TOURISM AND ICTS FOR VISITORS. THE CASE OF THE 'SEA AND LAND' NATIONAL PARK OF THE ATLANTIC ISLANDS

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to present a study of the virtual guides –with multimedia portable information– available for the 'Sea and Land' National Park of the Atlantic Islands in Galicia. Notwithstanding technical limitations, the use of multimedia guides in natural environments offers a plenty of advantages, especially where offering information on analogue supports is difficult or not desired. A natural environment is a place to be explored, where pleasure, physical activity, land navigation, contemplation of the landscape and knowledge are strongly linked and a multimedia portable guide can enlarge this "experience in the nature". The used of multimedia guides can be rated as positive: some of the m-learning advantages are widely implemented (specially in the use of audio files, and portable information), but also some given functions are constricted by technical and conceptual handicaps that may limit the visitors' interest to use this services.

Keywords: natural guide, natural heritage, outdoor tourism, virtual guide

1 Multimedia and virtual guides for touristic purposes in outdoors locations

Environmental education and approaches to biological life and ecosystems may benefit most from the use of m-learning as a powerful tool to enhance knowledge, and as an added marketing tool target to gain new visitors. In contrast to city locations (urban outdoors) or indoors locations, non-urban outdoor spaces (referred to as outdoors from this point) are environments with limitations for analogical information facilities, having in most cases a lack of infrastructure at the points of interest (POIs). Outside museums or visitor information offices, a natural environment cannot be restricted to an exhibition room or information panels. A natural environment is a place to be explored, where pleasure, physical activity, land navigation, contemplation of the landscape and knowledge are strongly linked: what could be called an "experience in the nature". Its implementation needs to be designed to satisfy the needs of the public, and to offer a more intense experience in the nature under the universal principle of design for learning. This involving multisensory, multimodal learning nature by touching, seeing, listening, smelling, and tasting (Sonneveld, Ludden, and Schifferstein, 2008). City-multimedia guides and touristic services based upon geolocation technologies (GPS location, Wi-Fi hotspot location, geotagging, geo-referenced content of points of interest –POI–...) are becoming increasingly popular. There is also a third kind of use where m-learning profits from the flexibility and mobility offered by this technology; outdoor activities in natural spaces. This form of nomadic inquiry (Hsi, 2003) may be of special interest not just to offer independent access to information but also to generate spatially situated knowledge (Kukulska-Hulme et al, 2009).

At the present we may notice a lack of specific portable multimedia guides or at least natural guides developed or adapted for PDAs and tables for natural spaces in Spain. Technically, multimedia guides for outdoor use have to deal with four main handicaps in the wild: nonexistent, weak or broken data connection, adverse light conditions for LCD displays (both capacitive or resistive), limited battery life and malfunction under adverse weather (rain or extreme temperatures). Notwithstanding technical limitations, the use of multimedia guides

in natural environments offers a plenty of advantages, especially where offering information on analogue supports is difficult or not desired. In the near future, considerable development of the technical possibilities of new devices is expected, this will allow new and more sophisticated functions, but for learning purposes we should focus on the opportunity such initiatives create for developing more advance ways of knowledge acquisition. By the moment visitors of natural spaces are limited to web virtual guides (not optimized for PDAs or tables screen sizes), indeed these guides content mostly digitalized information of previous sources and images designed as a printed guide, this means explanatory texts and exemplifying photos, occasionally panoramic videos and audio samples of birds¹. The opportunity to access to online information on a natural area is the great value for pedagogic purposes, in this case the access to information is only possible previous or after, not during the visit. Situated information is the main advantage of the use of portable digital guides, thus the information must be, first, developed and implemented for the technical requirements of PADs and tables. And, second, a global concept is needed in order to integrated the pedagogical and the touristic aspects, targeting to two different aims, one for environmental education and one to offer services of visitor interest (routes, how to get to, reservations...)².

An analysis of the information offered, and how it is offered in such multimedia outdoor guides is necessary to develop multimedia guides with both educational and touristic value. The central question is how bringing contents to an electronic gadget can create other wider benefits, rather than simply shifting the material support of the information, from analogue to digital. We should also consider that the perception and expectations of the part of the public in the use of ICTs for educational and tourist purposes present a complex image (Walker, 208). ITCs are not expected to be implemented as a current form of the text panel, the catalogue, or the information in images, audio, multimedia guides in portable devices, etc ... but as tools which enrich the visit not only offering information but more customized, with different discourses and, mainly with possibilities of experimenting and living a cognitive and sensory enriched experience. This makes us think about a use of ITCs where the visitor takes an active part in knowledge and is not a mere consumer of information. On the other hand, we have to assume that the resource of ITCs as a tool directed to achieve a greater participation of public and a more active experience must be in consonance with the expectations of visitors. This leaves us in the expectation by the visitors of natural spaces towards a use of technologies (digital or analog) which operate in all spheres of human perception (visual, olfactory, taste, auditory and tactile).

The digital visitor guides for the 'Sea and Land' National Park of the Atlantic Islands fulfill some of the advances functionalities of a digital portable guide targeted for the general public, with both aims didactic and touristic oriented, with pedagogical contents and useful infos for visitors. Our aim is to present and analyze the strong and weak points of this guides under several perspectives, from formal to conceptual, from usability to contents.

¹ For example the multimedia guide of the Málaga Mountains Natural Park, <http://montesdemalaga.org/index.html>, retrieved 3rd May, 2012.

² The following examples of digital portable guides could be considered: NABU-AlbEntdecker for the Alb Mountains in South Germany (<http://www.nabu-albentdecker.de>), iWebPark SNP for the Swiss National Park in East Switzerland (<http://www.nationalPark.ch/go/de/besuchen/wandern/digitaler-guide-webParksnp>) or the Northumberland Rock Art (<http://rockart.ncl.ac.uk/interactive/>, <http://rockartmobile.wordpress.com/>) (Galani et al. 2011). All of them have different functionalities and conceptions, but all of them seek for alternatives to the static, print-like guides, taking advance of the possibilities of the ubiquitous learning.

2 The digital visitor guides for the 'Sea and Land' National Park of the Atlantic Islands

The 'Sea and Land' National Park of the Atlantic Islands is situated around the Southern Coast of Galicia. The park consists of four island groups (Cíes, Ons, Salvora and Cortegada) with an area of 1.200 hectares and 7.200 sea miles. It is a sea and land ecosystem at three levels: underwater, intertidal zone and emerged land. It was created in 2002, with an increasing number of visitors since its creation³, thus a high potential for a multimedia or digital portable guide.

This park has two guides based on information offered on the internet pages as virtual visits, one provided by the Park Agency⁴, and the other provided by the Spanish Network of National Parks⁵. A two-headed administration structure is the origin of this overlap, the Park Agency responsible for the management of the Park belongs to the Galician Government, whilst the Spanish Network of National Parks is division within the Spanish Department of Environment, Rural and Maritime Affairs, which determines the environmental conservation guidelines of all national Parks in Spain.

In both cases the guides consist of web contents and visitors' guides with some possibility to be used in a PDA, in any case they are not really designed as multimedia PDA guides, furthermore the websites are not optimized for PDAs. Although the information provided by both sites is about the same locations, it is not systematic, the sites are not directly linked. Only in one case where a link in some PDF documents of the first web (Park Agency) redirects to the second (Spanish Network of National Parks). The information given in both sites is not identical, so we will be taking both in consideration here. In a real situation the visitor could get into the Park with two different guides systems with different contents and structures.

2.1 Park Site: Information for the Visitor

At the first site (provided by the Park Agency) the visitor can access the multimedia contents by selecting the heading Information for the Visitor. The structure of the information is as follows: a link to each Island group (for all the same under-headings: how to get to the Island, facilities, activities, download flyer), recommendations (for visitor), know more (about physical world, fauna, flora, sea-life, history/archeology, very similar info also available as PDF file), audio-guides (for ten routes), addresses of interest (Park administrations, facilities...).

Visitor information >	
Cíes >	How to get to
	Facilities
	Activities
	Download flyer
Ons >	[same as Cíes]

³ In 2002 the number of visitors was 192.579, in 2011: 322.296, from: http://reddeparquesnacionales.mma.es/parques/cies/guia_info_visitantes.htm, retrieved 30 April, 2012.

⁴ From: http://www.parquenacionalillasatlanticas.com/glg/informacion_audioguias.php/ Retrieved 2nd Mai, 2012.

⁵ From: <http://reddeparquesnacionales.mma.es/parques/cies/> Retrieved, 2nd Mai, 2012.

Cortegada >	[same as Cíes]
Sálvora >	[same as Cíes]
Recommendations >	Visitors' recommendations and rules. What is not allowed
To know more >	Physical World
	Fauna
	Flora
	Sea-life
	History/Archeology
Audio-guides >	Cíes (4 routes), Ons (4), Cortegada (2)
Addresses of interest >	Park office, authorities, ferries, accommodation/eating, councils, tourism info, others

Table 1. Structure of the 'Sea and Land' National Park of the Atlantic Islands – Park Agency Web

For every island group it is possible to print or download a PDF file with a sketch of the islands including the line of the proposed routes and the POIs (geographical references, facilities and restricted areas). For every route the visitor can preload on their PDA or mp3 player the audio files (mp3 format) with the spoken tour through the route. Short information about every route is also provided on the site with information on distance, estimated time and difficulty level of the track (without an explanation of the difficulty level), a general description and more information on the track (slope, circular or one way route, POIs) is also provided, for eight routes of ten suggested routes. Only information for the emerged land is provided, with special attention to vegetal and animal life, geographical POIs and historical/cultural issues. Also under the heading Know More, it is possible to access general information for all the islands regarding natural life and cultural issues. This information is also offered as PDF file in DIN A4 (21x29,7 cm) text document layout: physical world (12 pages, size 4,1 MB), fauna (11 pages, 852 KB), flora (24 pages, 6,1 MB), sea-life (22 pages, 10,6 MB), history/archeology (23 pages, 8 MB). In short, not really implemented to be viewed in a PDA.

Under the heading Audio-Guides the visitor can download the linked audio files for the routes and a map of the routes at each island as PDF file; Ons: 303 KB size –DIN A4 format–, Cíes: 614 KB size –DIN A4 format– and Cortegada: 713 KB size –87,07x62,48 cm–. The map for the Cortegada Island appears as photo illustrating the text (jpg file, 66 KB, 762x489 pixels), the downloadable file is a topographic map with no route information or POIs. There are audio guides for three of the four island groups (Cíes –four routes–, Ons –four–, Cortegada –one with two alternatives–). An audio guide can be downloaded compiled in a folder, every folder contains a number of mp3 files depending on the POIs at the route, the audio guide is a sample of short explanations of the points tagged at the maps included in the flyers. The audio folders have a size between 28,6 MB (Lighthouse Peak Route at Cíes Islands) and 6 MB (Castle Route at Ons Island), the single audio files between 6,3 MB and 415 KB. Each folder has a duration between 24 minutes and 15 seconds (Lighthouse Peak Route, Cíes Islands) and 5m32s (Castle Route, Ons Islands). The number of single audio-files per folder varies from fifteen (Lighthouse Peak Route, Cíes Islands) to seven (Castle and Lighthouse Routes, Ons Islands). This leads to an audio-guide system that makes demands on the listener's patience through both the long duration of the audio files, and their varying length.

Except for the audio files, all the information in both cases above does not consist of material designed specifically for PDA use, a flyer is available for every island group (four in total). The doubled-sided flyers (see Fig 1) have an original print size of 42,88x21 cm –pro face– and a file size of around 1,2 MB. In addition, the page layout (colors, font size, text/image box distribution...) makes the documents unsuitable for a PDA display. The flyers include a general introduction to the Park, a brief description of the routes (shorter than at the internet site but with maps and photos of the POIs), and advice to park visitors (including regulations concerning pets, waste, noise and camping).

Fig 1. Flyer of the Cies Island Group

On the website it is possible to read the information in Galician, Spanish or English; the Galician and the Spanish on-line text versions are original, the English one is a translation provided by the Google Translate service (clicking on English, a menu with all the languages available is displayed). But the information is not consistent between languages. It seems that, for some reason, some material was elaborated in one of the two main languages in Galicia and it was uploaded to the web without any language principle. The visitor may be surprised by the random and unclear use of the language. This is also true for the English and other language versions of the site, taking into consideration that the audio files and flyers are the

same as those in Galician or Spanish above, we may conclude that the site does not provide a real multilingual guide facility.

2.2 The Park Site: Virtual visit

In the second site (provided by the Spanish Network of National Parks) we will focus on the information presented under the headings Visitor's Guide and Virtual Visit, although the Virtual Guide provides material for a visit at ground level. An open question is whether this visitor guide was thought as a virtual web-based guide or as information to be used at the location, some parts of it appears targeted in this direction, although this aim isn't fulfilled. In conception, it is not very different from the Park Agency page. In this case there is only static visual information available at the site (text documents, photos, audio files and maps). All the visitor's guide information is only provided in Spanish, even though there is a menu option for other languages.

Fig 2. Web view of the Visitor's Guide

Under the heading Virtual Visit a menu is displayed in which the user can click on three items: flora, fauna and routes. Under Flora the same common window is showed, on its left side a list of plants can be seen, clicking on the single link a photo and a brief explanation of the plan is given; the same procedure is used for Fauna. The items are listed alphabetically by their common name. The text explanations are not systematic descriptions of the plants and animals, for example, in some cases the taxonomic category of a plant or animal is given, in many not, moreover the descriptions are sometimes centered on the characteristics of the plant/animal, sometimes on their ecological value or rarity, without morphological description. The texts are in a simple language, except for a few specialist terms familiar to natural scientists, such as 'dioecious'. Due to the reduced built-in window size and reduced font size this site is also not suitable for a PDA display. The only audio files are linked to bird items, for nearly every bird a song sample is provided (around five-seconds duration per sample). Under routes the user is redirected to the heading Activities of the Visitor Guide.

The Visitor Guide consists of six sections, in this order: Location, Park Map, Permits, General Information and Activities, and a link to double-sided flyer with general information,

this information is given only in paper form (PDF file, size 1,1 MB, 44,6 × 60,61 cm pro face) and it is not shown directly on screen. As in the example given above, the document (structure, font size, colors, photos and maps) is laid out as a poster and not suitable to be read using a digital device.

Virtual Visit >	
Fauna >	[contents]
Flora >	[contents]
Routes >	Ons Island Routes
	Cíes Island Routes
Visitor's Guide >	
Flyer: general information >	[pdf]
Location >	[contents]
Park Maps >	General, Cíes, Ons, Sálvora, Cortegada maps
Permits >	Anchoring, diving, for camping
General information >	Facilities, authorities and services [blank]
	Recommendations: links, routes, recommendations
	Park rules
	Visitors number
	Natural environment:
	Councils
	Natural and cultural heritage:
Activities >	Routes [same as under Virtual Visit]

Table 2. Structure of the 'Sea and Land' National Park of the Atlantic Islands – Spanish Network of National Parks Web

Location. This leads us to a short explanation of the Park's location and a sketched map of all the islands forming the Park. This general map can also be downloaded as a jpeg file (size 299 KB, 2195x3160 pixels), but it remains an overview map. A link to how to get to the Park is provided, as well as written information about the ferry transport to the Cíes and Ons Islands is provided but not for the Cortegada and Sálvora Islands. Another sketched map of the ferry connections from the mainland to the island is displayed (JPEG file, 221 KB, 1174x1667 pixels).

Park Maps. The next link to Park Maps offers the possibility to download five maps in PDF format, one general (the same two maps as in heading Location, but put together in a different format –size 737 KB, DIN A4 format–) and one for each Island group, in this case these are topographic maps with geographical (rather than tourist) information. The technical features of the maps are as follows: Cíes, –2,4 MB, 19,41x27,73 cm– Ons –1,3 MB, 19,41x27,73 cm–, Cortegada –2,2 MB, 19,58x28,12 cm– and Sálvora –1,4 MB, 19,44x27,73 cm–. Once again the visitor has to deal with maps which are oversized and inadequate for a PDA. Printing the maps is the best option.

Permits. For camping it is possible to link to the online reservation centers for each island. For anchoring and diving, paper forms can be downloaded from the site, for navigation

an extra link to an on-line request is provided. Surprisingly, under this link, redirecting to a new site⁶, the information is provided in Galician, Spanish and English.

General Information. Besides to the flyer with general information, some other facts already given under other headings are repeated here. It is divided in the following items: (a) Facilities, info points and services (containing brief information on: visitors' centers, the park administration office and camping facilities). (b) Recommendations. (c) Park rules. (d) Visitor numbers: a graph showing the visitor number trends from 2002 to 2010. (e) Environment. This leads to extended texts on four general topics –physical world, sea world, on land world (flora/fauna), and conservation and biodiversity–, some information given here also differs from the information available at Virtual Visit. (f) Councils opens a table with the links to the local councils in the Park. (g) Historic and cultural heritage, a succinct introduction to heritage value of the Islands can be read here.

Activities. In this case the visitor is redirected to the same information included under the topic Routes in the Virtual Guide.

3 From digitalized information to digital guides

In our two cases of study we can find different ways to access information but not a real alternative to traditional learning strategies beyond personal access to given contents. The visitor can select which items they want to check and when they do so, by using some kind of travel guide with dynamic documents, but the learning strategies remain the same as in conventional learning. The Sea and Land' National Park of the Atlantic Island digital guides couldn't properly be considered a multimedia guide or even a virtual visit due to this lack of structure and usability, it is more an attempt to offer the visitor the possibility to download digitalized infos (audio, images and texts) into a PDA, with a closed and static structure. Considering the principles of e-learning –portability, connectivity, flexibility, instantly communication, motivation and active learning experiences– (Knight, 2005) no many of them are to find in these guides. Using as reference functions found in other portable multimedia guides (Casado-Neira, 2012) the 'Sea and Land' National Park of the Atlantic Islands guides fulfill part of them, adding and extra value to the web based information, but a multimedia or digital portable guide may still be developed with the aim of offering an dynamic situated information system previous, during and after the visit at the location.

Features	Implemented	Features	Implemented
Specific Contents	No	Geolocation	No
PDA adapted Infos	No	Static Maps	Yes
Texts	Yes	Dynamic Maps	No
Audios	Yes	Additional Infos	Yes
Photos	Yes	Games/Simulations	No
Videos	No	Self Research	No
Augmented reality	No	Guided Visit	Yes
Specific App.	No	Web info	Yes

Table 3. Features in the 'Sea and Land' National Park of the Atlantic Islands guide

The basis of m-learning is a located (in time and space) learning experience, some authors (Kambourakis, Kontoni, and Sapounas, 2004) consider m-learning a way of obtaining

⁶ From: <http://www.iatlanticas.es/> Retrieved 2nd Mai, 2012.

knowledge outside of space/time parameters, but otherwise the main benefit of m-learning is the possibility to generate space/time related knowledge, some basic examples of this can be found in the use of city guides based on augmented reality or applications for location sharing, like 'find my friends' –both based on space location, or communication services for instant messaging or flowing reports –both based on synchronicity–. Thus m-learning is portable but not necessarily decontextualised and we may consider spatial/time contextualisation as its main, but not sole, advantage.

Due to the fast development of new gadgets and applications created for PDAs and similar (mainly by the rise of App On-line Shops) it does not seem possible to define a static and closed corpus of functions and characteristics of multimedia or digital portable guides, other than that of nomadic inquiry. Otherwise, even regarding the features given to m-learning (Yahua, Arniza, and Abd, 2010): permanency, accessibility, immediacy of the information for learners and context-awareness; all of them are related to the access to information, not to the advantages for developing the visitor knowledge in a natural environment.

Self-researching (Marsick & Watkins, 2001) is the gate that connects to the nuclear qualities of m-, and e-learning as well as learning strategies based upon social, constructivist and collaborative principles. But there is a lack of features, that may be considered fundamental to achieve this active visit experience, like on-line info updates (based on dynamic database with up to data contents), extendable and durable contents (possibility of acceding to the contents after or previous to the visit, links to further information, eventually storage for off-line use), personalization (preferences based user's profile, information adapted to the user's profile), collaborative work (connection between gadgets for cooperative learning) and social networking (users' valuations and reviews, file share features, microblogging). Despite the remarkable chances for nomadic inquiring, contents are not everything, and in the two cases here analyzed only a personalized, collaborative and deeper visit and learning experience can be offered with limitations.

4 Conclusion

For the two guides here presented, attending to the formal aspects only the formal variables can be considered (information type, information structure), for the other ones (usability, quantity, substantiality, applicability) is necessary to carry out tests with visitors in experimental research. In this context 'easiness' is synonymous for user usability, 'quality' refers to the information a person can earn –it has not to do with the quantity of information is offered, but with the information absorbed by the person, thus it is an individual measurable value–, 'substantiality' –also individual and measurable in the time–, and 'applicability', using the information/skills learned to deal with a problem or to enlarge own knowledge. 'Applicability' is the key of all four elements because it turns information into knowledge, obviously it can only be measure at personal level and in problem solving situations. Educational purposes and demands of visitors must be taken in account in order to develop a multimedia or digital portable guide, which can be an added value to the personal vivid experience of the natural environment.

In resumé, the used of multimedia guides and virtual visits can be rated as positive: some of the ubiquitous advantages are widely implemented (specially in the use of audio and video files, and located information). On the other hand some given functions are constricted by technical handicaps and the information provided, in many cases, does not suppose a significant quality shift from conventional information panels or printed guides (static information, not user adaptive, poor self exploring functions...). Despite the remarkable chances for nomadic inquiring, contents are not everything, and in the two cases here analyzed only with limitations a personalized experience can be offered. A deep concept has

to be achieved for natural environments where pleasure, physical activity, land navigation, contemplation of the landscape and knowledge are strongly linked.

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